

Aza Triterpenes—III[†] : Action of Excess Hydrazoic Acid-Boron Trifluoride Etherate on 3-Oxo-Penta Cyclic Triterpenes

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3-Oxo-pentacyclic triterpenes (I, II and III) furnished 3-cyano-4-azido-3,4-seco penta cyclic triterpenes (IB, IIB and IIIB) on treatment with excess $N_2H \cdot BF_3$ etherate both in benzene and chloroform media. The reaction did not proceed at 10° . Attempts to build up tetrazole ring system by the action of excess N_2H -conc. H_2SO_4 on 3-oxo-penta cyclic triterpenes (I, II and III) furnished lactams (IA, IIA and IIIA). The lactams were recovered unreacted on treatment with excess $N_2H \cdot BF_3$ etherate.

SCHMIDT reaction of ketones with equimolecular quantities of hydrazoic acid yields amides and with excess of hydrazoic acid tetrazoles. Tetrazoles are known to possess biological activity and some are of clinical significance. The tetrazole obtained from cyclohexanone, commercially known as metrazole or cardiazole, is a heart stimulant^{1,2}. Steroidal tetrazoles are claimed to possess anti-fertility and anti-spermatogenic activity^{3,4}.

A search in literature revealed that Schmidt reaction with excess of hydrazoic acid-boron trifluoride etherate on triterpene ketones has not been studied. In the present investigation lupenone (I), methyl betulonate (II) and methyl oleanonate (III) were treated with excess hydrazoic acid in presence of freshly distilled boron trifluoride etherate in benzene and chloroform media for 16 hr and 3 hr at room temperature. The reaction products in all the above three cases did not show characteristic absorption for tetrazole ring system in their ir spectra. The ir spectra were also lacking in 7-membered lactam carbonyl absorption, indicating that the reaction did not proceed to give either the tetrazole ring system or the normal Schmidt reaction product. Instead, the ir spectra of the reaction products showed absorption around 2250 cm^{-1} and 2050 cm^{-1} , characteristic of nitrile and azide groups, respectively. This is possible only when there is cleavage in ring A of these triterpene ketones.

The ring fission in the presence of excess hydrazoic acid-boron trifluoride etherate is not uncommon though not a usual feature. The 17-oxo steroids, esteron methyl ether⁵ and 4-androstene-3,17-dione^{6,7}, gave besides tetrazoles, 13, 17-seco-13 α -azido-17-nitriles. 5 α -Hydroxy-6-oxo-5 α -cholestan⁸ furnished 3 β -acetoxy-5-oxo-5,6-secocholestan-6-nitrile. On the basis of formation of lactams (IA, IIA and IIIA) in the normal Schmidt reaction of these triterpene ketones (I, II and III)⁹, ir spectra and analytical data, 3-cyano-4-azido-3,

4-seco structures were assigned to the reaction products (IB, IIB and IIIB). The cleavage of C_3-C_4 bond in this reaction is in conformation with the results of Beckmann rearrangement⁹ of the oximes of lupenone, methyl betulonate and methyl oleanonate. These triterpenes have a gem-dimethyl group adjacent to 6-membered keto function. As in the case of Beckmann rearrangement, even in the present instance the gem-dimethyl group next to oxo function is responsible for the cleavage of C_3-C_4 bond. The signal at δ 2.5 (2H) in the nmr spectrum of IB can be assigned to $-CH_2-C \equiv N$ supporting the 3-cyano-4-azido-3,4-seco structure.

In an attempt to build up the tetrazole ring system the reaction was conducted at 10° but the compounds were recovered unreacted both in benzene and chloroform media. The 3-oxo-pentacyclic triterpenes (I, II and III) furnished normal Schmidt reaction products (IA, IIA and IIIA) with excess of hydrazoic acid-conc. sulphuric acid both in benzene and chloroform media. For the formation of tetrazoles or the lactams, imido carbonium ion is the intermediate¹⁰ which reacts with water present in sulphuric acid in preference to hydrazoic acid. Treatment of the lactams (IA, IIA and IIIA) with excess of hydrazoic acid-boron trifluoride etherate both in benzene and chloroform media proved unsuccessful in building the tetrazole ring system probably the lactam, once formed, is stable enough not to revert to imido carbonium ion which is a precursor for the formation of tetrazoles.

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Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. All the compounds showed consistent elemental analysis. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr.

1. *Preparation of hydrazoic acid in benzene and chloroform media*: A stirred solution of sodium azide (100 g) in water (250 ml) was cooled to 5-10° and benzene or chloroform (1 l) was added followed by drop-wise addition of conc. sulphuric acid (93 ml) during 30 min at 5-10°. The mixture was stirred for 30 min with temperature kept below 10°. The organic layer was separated and dried.

2. *Action of excess hydrazoic acid-boron trifluoride etherate on 3-oxo-pentacyclic-triterpenes (I, II, III) in benzene at room temperature*: Isolation of 3-cyano-4-azido-3,4-seco pentacyclic triterpenes (IB, IIB and IIIB): A typical experiment is described. To 3-oxo-pentacyclic triterpene (1.5 g) in benzene (100 ml), freshly distilled boron trifluoride etherate (10 ml) and hydrazoic acid solution in benzene (200 ml) were added and the mixture kept for 16 hr at room temperature (30-35°). Crushed ice was added to the reaction mixture and the organic layer was washed with ice-cold water. The benzene layer was dried and evaporated. The residue was adsorbed over a column of neutral alumina (50 g) and eluted with benzene (500 ml) and chloroform (500 ml). The benzene eluate gave 3-cyano-4-azido-3,4-seco pentacyclic triterpene (750 mg), crystallising from methanol as colourless needles. Chloroform eluate did not yield any residue on removal of the solvent.

The reaction was conducted in chloroform medium at room temperature for 16 hr and 3 hr duration. The reaction product was 3-cyano-4-azido-3,4-seco pentacyclic triterpene, m.p.: IB 220°, IIB 215° and IIIB 215°. IR: IB 2250 cm^{-1} and 2050 cm^{-1} ; IIB 2250 cm^{-1} and 2040 cm^{-1} and IIIB 2235 cm^{-1} and 2045 cm^{-1} for -CN and N₃ groups, respectively. NMR for IB δ 2.5(2H for -CH₂-C≡N).

3. *Action of excess hydrazoic acid on 3-oxo-pentacyclic triterpene in presence of conc. sulphuric acid in benzene*: Isolation of 3-oxo-3a-aza-A-homo pentacyclic triterpenes (IA, IIA and IIIA): A typical experiment is described. To 3-oxo-pentacyclic triterpene (1.5 g) in benzene (100 ml), conc. sulphuric acid (3 ml) and hydrazoic acid in benzene (200 ml) were added and kept for 16 hr at room temperature (30-35°). Crushed ice was added to the reaction mixture and the organic layer was washed with ice-cold water. The benzene layer was dried and evaporated. The residue (900 mg) was adsorbed over a column of neutral alumina (50 g) and eluted with benzene (500 ml) and chloroform (500 ml). The benzene eluate did not yield any residue on removal of the solvent. Chloroform eluate yielded 3-oxo-3a-aza-A-homo pentacyclic triterpene, identical with the product obtained in the Schmidt reaction of 3-oxo-pentacyclic triterpene⁹, m.p.: IA 258°; IIA 256°; IIIA 258° (lit⁹ m.p.s 258, 256 and 258 for IA, IIA and IIIA, respectively).

IR: IA 3230 cm^{-1} and 1675 cm^{-1} ; IIA 3225 cm^{-1} and 1675 cm^{-1} ; IIIA 3220 cm^{-1} and 1675 cm^{-1} for NH and -CONH respectively. NMR IIIA δ 5.5 (H) exchangeable with D₂O for NH.

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